

A Study on Visualising the TED Talks Statistics to Understand the Most Trending Topic

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TED talks aim to democratize knowledge. Nowadays it produces more than 200 talks per year addressing dozens of different topics. Despite the critics who claim that TED talks reduce complex ideas to 20-minute autobiographical stories of inspiration, the great influence they have on the knowledge diffusion in our society is undeniable. Where in the world popular ted talks and speakers are gaining more importance. This study aims at visualizing the popular TED talks events, TED speakers and tags that are widely searched. The study uses Power BI & MS-Excel to create visualization and dashboards the data analysed.

INTRODUCTION

TED is a non-profit devoted to spreading ideas, usually in the form of short, powerful talks (18 minutes or less). TED began in 1984 as a conference where Technology, Entertainment and Design converged, and today covers almost all topics — from science to business to global issues — in more than 100 languages. Meanwhile, independently run TEDx events help share ideas in communities around the world.

It is a video created from a presentation at the main TED (technology, entertainment, design) conference or one of its many satellite events around the world.

TED talks are limited to a maximum length of 18 minutes but may be on any topic. Here's the TEDx website's explanation of selection criteria: "TED looks for engaging, charismatic speakers whose talks expose new ideas that are supported by concrete evidence and are relevant to a broad, international audience."

Over the years, presenters of TED talks have included Al Gore, Bill Clinton, Bill Gates, Bono, Jane Goodall, Malcolm Gladwell, Gordon Brown, Richard Dawkins Mike Rowe, Larry Page, Sergey Brin and Vint Cerf.

NEED OF THE STUDY:

TED Foundation is to foster the spread of great ideas. It gives importance, to provide a platform for thinkers, visionaries and teachers, so that people around the globe can gain a better understanding of the biggest issues faced by the world, and feed a desire to help create a better future. Therefore, the present study is undertaken to visualise the ted talk's statistics and to understand the most trending topic.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- 1) To study about the most popular global TED talk speaker
- 2) To find out the top 10 popular global TED talk Speakers based on number of views.
- 3) To analyse the top 10 TED talk tags based on globally popular TED events.
- 4) To study about the globally popular TED speakers' occupation

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

This study was to understand the TED talk's statistics and visually represent the popular TED talks. Specifically, the study sought to describe the ranked importance i.e. One of the most important factors in TED talk's vast popularity is that they are available online, anytime, to anyone, and for no cost. While the original TED conferences were more elite and expensive to attend, now anyone can benefit from the information and inspiration, even if on a limited budget.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Yu-jung Chang, Hung-Tzu Huangb, "Exploring TED Talks as a Pedagogical Resource for Oral Presentations: A Corpus-Based Move Analysis" in English Teaching & Learning, 2015, "The objective of the study was to examine the rhetorical structure of talks from TED conferences to explore the possibility of their being incorporated into the instruction of oral presentation in English-language classrooms. The methodology used for this study was compiled using 950 oral presentations extracted from the TED website. Findings from our analysis also demonstrate that TED speakers tend to include listener orientation and speaker presentation throughout the talks."

Martínez Hernández María A.1, Vargas Cuevas Junior, "TED Talks as an ICT Tool to Promote Communicative Skills in EFL Students" English Language Teaching, 2018, "the objective of the study was to propose a reflection on the incidence of TED talks on the teaching and learning of English as a foreign language. The methodology used were interviews, questionnaires, and teacher journals. TED talks prove to be a useful material for English teaching as a foreign language considering that they assemble many characteristics that catch students' attention and get them related with the language spoken in actual contexts."

Alison McGregor, University of Texas at Austin Beth Zielinski, Macquarie University, “AN EXPLORATION OF TEACHING INTONATION USING A TED TALK” In J. Levis, H. Le., I. Lucic, E. Simpson, & S. Vo (Eds). *Proceedings of the 7th Pronunciation in Second Language Learning and Teaching Conference, 2016*, “the objective of the study was investigated the intonation of a TED Talk in a multi-layered approach – interpretatively, perceptually and acoustically. To identify the features produced in the monologic speech sample of a speaker of North American English”. The methodology used for this study was for the acoustic analysis of pauses, pitch range, and prominence. Findings Support the contextualized teaching of intonation as well as pedagogical use of rich TED Talk speech sample.

Prof. Reima Al-Jarf King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, “TED Talks as a Listening Resource in the EFL College Classroom” in *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*, 2021, “The objective of the study was to listening skills that can be developed, and an instructional strategy. TTs provide a variety of real-life themes, speakers, motivation, and inspiration”. Findings showed that the students responded very positively to this new type of instruction and were satisfied with the improvement they made in their English language skills.

Shelestova Tatyana¹, Kalizhanova Anna^{1,2*}, “The advantages of using TED talks materials in ESL classrooms” in *Journal for Educators, Teachers and Trainers*, Vol. 12 (2), 2021, “The objective of the study was to advantages of TED Talks materials as their authenticity, availability, variety, utility, user-friendly usability of the website with the materials, and the existence of scripts for each video”. The methodology for this study was for the, vectors of competence development (Scientific project on grant financing of the MES of the RK). Finding specific terms, synonyms for certain words, as well as finding more accessible contextual information on the topic or subject of a conversation. The conclusion of this topic, we will show how students’ language skills have changed according to CEFR.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on secondary data. Data is collected from a public source through internet. (www.kaggle.com) This data sets consists of speaker name and occupation duration,

Tools & Techniques:

- Microsoft Excel
- Power BI

INFERENCE 6.1: ANALYSIS ON POPULAR TED TALK SPEAKER IN THE WORLD BASED ON VIEWS (YOUTUBE)

RANK	SPEAKER	VIEW S	Country of origin
1	Ken Robinson	63006281	Liverpool England
Name	Ken Robinson		
Published date	Jan 7, 2007		
Speaker occupation	Author & Educator		
title	Do schools kill creativity?		
comments	4553		
description on	Sir Ken Robinson makes an entertaining and profoundly moving case for creating an education system that nurtures (rather than undermines) creativity.		
duration	1164		
event	TED2006		
film date	Feb 26, 2006		
languages	60		

Interpretation: It is observed from the above table that ‘Ken Robinson’ an author and educator by profession is found as the most popular global TED talk speaker based on the highest number of views.

INFERENCE 6.2: Analysis on TOP TEN TED SPEAKERS BASED ON VIEWS (YOUTUBE)

INTERPRETATION:

It is observed from the above table and graph that Ken Robinson, Amy Cuddy, Breen Brown are the top 3 speakers TED speakers who had maximum views on YouTube. 60% of the popular speaker’s origin is United States.

INFERENCE 6.3: Analysis on popular tags for top 10 TED TALKS based on views (YouTube)

INTERPRETATION:

It is observed from the above table and graph that tags for which the TED event has high views are children, creativity, culture, dance, education, parenting, teaching -TED2006Body language, brain, business, Psychology, self, Success- TED2006books, culture, History, Humour, science, writing- TEDGlobal2012 Culture, sound, Speech-TEDGlobal2013Business, Culture, Entertainment, Goal setting, Motivation, Potential, Psychology-TED20

INFERENCE 6.4: Analysis on popular top 10 TED events based on views (YouTube)

INTERPRETATION:

It is observed from the above visual presentation that, TED 2006 event is globally popular. It also has Ken Robinson’s talk in the event that had globally highest views. Other popular events are TED Global 2012,

INFERENCE 6.5: Analysis on occupation of the popular speaker

INTERPRETATION:

The above mentioned are the top 10 speakers, their occupation and country of origin

-Ken Robin’s son is the best speaker whose occupation is Author& Educator his country of origin is Liverpool England - Amy Cuddy is the next best speaker whose occupation is social psychologist, his country of origin is Pennsylvania

INFERENCE 6.6: Listing the top 10 TED speakers and gender dominance

INTERPRETATION:

It is observed from the table and graph 60% of male top 10 global speakers and 40% of female speakers

INFERENCE 7: Visually presenting all the above data in dashboard

FINDINGS:

It has been Observed that Ken Robinson has highest views on Ted talk as a speaker. From the study it has been found that the top 10 ted speakers who has maximum views and comments worldwide ted websites. It is observed that 60% of the top 10 global speakers are male and 40% female speakers among worldwide. It is observed from the above table and graph that tags for which

the TED event has high views are children, creativity, culture, dance, education, parenting, teaching -TED2006. Ken Robin's son is the best speaker whose occupation is Author& Educator his country of origin is Liverpool England. Amy Cuddy is the next best speaker whose occupation is social psychologist; his country of origin is Pennsylvania.

CONCLUSION:

From the study identified two types of users:

The expert user, who watches TED talks a lot and desires to quickly identify a talk of interest;. The user, who watches TED Talks less frequently, and interested in browsing through the selections available and finding a video of interest.

References

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2. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329028486_TED_Talks_as_an ICT_Tool_to_Promote_Communicative_Skills_in_EFL_Students
3. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303921382_AN_EXPLORATION_OF_TEACHING_INTONATION_USING_A_TED_TALK
4. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354993844_TED_Talks_as_a_Listening_Resource_in_the_EFL_College_Classroom
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6. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334138417_Teaching_Business_English_with_TED_Talks_Putting_Ideas_into_Practice